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DEVELOPMENT OF A COSMECEUTICAL ANTI-ACNE CREAM BASED ON ROSA LAXA EXTRACT

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Abstract: *Acne vulgaris is one of the most common chronic inflammatory skin diseases associated with excessive sebum production, follicular hyperkeratinization, and bacterial colonization of hair follicles. Despite the availability of numerous topical agents, the development of effective and safe cosmeceutical products based on natural bioactive compounds remains an important research direction. The present study aimed to develop a technology for producing a cosmeceutical anti-acne cream containing an extract of Rosa laxa fruits. Pharmacognostic analysis of the plant material was performed, and ultrasonic extraction using ethanol solutions of different concentrations was carried out to obtain biologically active compounds. Several cream formulations were prepared and evaluated to determine the optimal composition. The developed cream contained hyaluronic acid, azelaic acid, vitamins A and E, orange essential oil, and Rosa laxa extract. The technological scheme for cream production was established, and the quality of the product was evaluated according to organoleptic and physicochemical parameters. The obtained results demonstrated that the developed cosmeceutical cream meets the requirements of cosmetic standards and may represent a promising natural anti-acne formulation.*

Keywords: *acne, cosmeceutical cream, formulation technology, Rosa laxa, rosehip extract*

Аннотация: *Акне обыкновенное является одним из наиболее распространённых хронических воспалительных заболеваний кожи, связанных с избыточной продукцией кожного сала, фолликулярной гиперкератинизацией и бактериальной колонизацией волосяных фолликулов. Несмотря на наличие многочисленных средств для местного применения, разработка эффективных и безопасных космецевтических продуктов на основе природных биологически активных соединений остаётся важным направлением исследований. Целью настоящего исследования являлась разработка технологии получения космецевтического крема против акне, содержащего экстракт плодов Rosa laxa. Был проведён фармакогностический анализ растительного сырья, а также выполнена ультразвуковая экстракция с использованием этанольных растворов различной концентрации для получения биологически активных соединений. Для определения оптимального состава были приготовлены и исследованы несколько вариантов кремовых композиций. Разработанный крем содержал гиалуроновую кислоту, азелаиновую кислоту, витамины А и Е, эфирное масло апельсина и экстракт Rosa laxa. Была разработана технологическая схема производства крема и проведена оценка качества продукта по органолептическим и физико-химическим показателям. Полученные результаты показали, что разработанный космецевтический крем соответствует требованиям косметических стандартов и может рассматриваться как перспективная натуральная формула для лечения акне.*

Ключевые слова: *акне, космецевтический крем, технология получения, Rosa laxa, экстракт шиповника*

Acne vulgaris is a chronic inflammatory skin disease affecting approximately 80–90% of adolescents and a considerable proportion of adults worldwide. The pathogenesis of acne is multifactorial and involves increased sebum production, follicular hyperkeratinization, inflammation, and colonization of hair follicles by Cutibacterium acnes (formerly Propionibacterium acnes) [1-6].

Conventional anti-acne therapies include antibiotics, retinoids, benzoyl peroxide, and azelaic acid. However, long-term use of synthetic drugs may cause adverse effects such as irritation, dryness,

and antibiotic resistance. Therefore, the development of cosmeceutical products based on natural plant extracts with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties has attracted increasing attention.

Plants of the genus *Rosa* are known to contain a wide range of biologically active compounds including ascorbic acid, flavonoids, phenolic acids, carotenoids, and tannins. These compounds exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and skin-protective properties.

Rosa laxa fruits are particularly rich in vitamin C and phenolic compounds that may contribute to skin regeneration, reduction of oxidative stress, and inhibition of inflammatory processes associated with acne.

Therefore, the aim of the present study was to develop a technology for producing a cosmeceutical cream containing *Rosa laxa* extract with potential anti-acne activity

The fruits of *Rosa laxa* were used as plant material. The samples were dried and subjected to pharmacognostic analysis to confirm their morphological and anatomical characteristics.

Ultrasonic extraction was used to obtain biologically active compounds from *Rosa laxa* fruits due to its efficiency and ability to preserve thermolabile substances. The dried fruits were ground and divided into four portions. Extraction was carried out using ethanol solutions of different concentrations: 90% ethanol, 70% ethanol, 50% ethanol, 30% ethanol, water. Extraction was performed in an ultrasonic bath for 30 minutes. The maximum extraction yield was obtained during ultrasonic extraction with 70% ethanol and reached 7.3%.

Several experimental formulations were prepared to determine the optimal composition of the cosmeceutical cream.

The selected formulation included the following components (%): Water - 75, hyaluronic acid - 0.2, azelaic acid - 5, polysorbate-80 - 1, *Rosa laxa* extract - 1, mentha essential oil 0.3, vitamin A- 1.5, vitamin E 1.5, olivem 1000 - 7, Sharomix 708 - 1.

Azelaic acid acts as an antimicrobial and keratolytic agent commonly used in acne treatment. Hyaluronic acid provides moisturizing and skin-repairing effects, while vitamins A and E act as antioxidants. The plant extract contributes additional anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity.

The cream was prepared using a two-phase emulsification method. The water phase consisted of water, hyaluronic acid, and azelaic acid. The mixture was heated to approximately 80 °C with constant stirring until complete dissolution of the components. The oil phase contained oils, fat-soluble vitamins, and the emulsifier Olivem 1000. Both phases were heated separately to approximately 70 °C and then combined by gradually adding the water phase to the oil phase with mechanical stirring (about 2000 rpm). After formation of the emulsion, polysorbate-80 was added to improve dispersion of the oil components. The mixture was cooled to 40 °C, after which the preservative Sharomix 708 was added. The finished cream was packed into sterile containers and allowed to stabilize at room temperature.

The quality of the developed cream was assessed according to the requirements of cosmetic standards (GOST R 52343-2005). The evaluated parameters included: appearance, color, odor, pH, thermal stability, colloidal stability.

The cream was characterized as a homogeneous mass with a characteristic odor and color. The pH value was approximately 6, which is compatible with the physiological pH of human skin. The formulation demonstrated good thermal and colloidal stability.

The development of plant-based cosmeceutical products is an important direction in modern dermatological and cosmetic research. The results obtained in this study indicate that *Rosa laxa* fruits may serve as a promising source of biologically active compounds for skin-care formulations.

The high content of ascorbic acid and phenolic compounds in rosehip fruits contributes to their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. These compounds may reduce oxidative stress and inhibit inflammatory processes involved in acne pathogenesis.

Azelaic acid included in the formulation is known to suppress the growth of *Cutibacterium acnes* and normalize keratinization processes. The combination of azelaic acid with plant extracts may enhance the therapeutic potential of the formulation.

Additionally, vitamins A and E contribute to skin regeneration and protection against oxidative damage. Hyaluronic acid improves skin hydration and barrier function, which is important for maintaining healthy skin.

The developed formulation therefore represents a multifunctional cosmeceutical product combining antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and moisturizing effects.

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